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Design, synthesis, and anticandidal evaluation of benzimidazole and imidazopyridine-based *N*-Acylhydrazones

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Abstract

A novel series of benzimidazole and imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-based *N*-acylhydrazones was designed, synthesized, and evaluated for antifungal activity against a clinical strain of *Candida albicans*. Structural elucidation was performed using ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy and High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS). *In vitro* antifungal testing revealed that several compounds exhibited moderate to strong anticandidal activity, with minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) ranging from 26.009 μM to 70.034 μM, compared to fluconazole as the reference drug. Structure–activity relationship (SAR) analysis demonstrated that lipophilic aryl substituents, particularly naphthalen-2-ol and aryl sulfane moieties, play a key role in enhancing antifungal efficacy, likely by promoting membrane permeability through increased hydrophobic interactions. Notably, compound **6a**, bearing a naphthalen-2-ol fragment, emerged as the most potent derivative. The results highlight the promising potential of *N*-acylhydrazone scaffolds, particularly those integrating sulfur-containing or polycyclic aromatic groups, as leads for the development of new antifungal agents targeting resistant *Candida albicans* strains.

Keywords: *N*-acylhydrazones; Benzimidazole; Imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine; Antifungal activity; *Candida albicans*

1. Introduction

Fungal infections remain a significant threat to human health, particularly among immunocompromised individuals. *Candida albicans* (*C. albicans*), a common fungal species in humans, is typically benign but can become pathogenic under certain conditions, leading to candidiasis [1]. It is the most frequent cause of fungemia worldwide and a leading opportunistic infection among individuals with HIV [2].

Although several antifungal therapies are available, treatment options remain limited to five major drug classes: allylamines, azoles, echinocandins, polyenes and pyrimidine analogs [3] [4] [5]. These treatments face growing challenges, including rising drug resistance undesirable side effects, and limited effectiveness against biofilm-associated infections [6] [7] [8]. Biofilms, which often develop on medical devices, significantly hinder treatment by creating barriers that conventional antifungal agents struggle to penetrate [9].

Despite antifungal treatment, *Candida* infections are associated with high mortality rates, sometimes reaching up to 40% [10] [11]. Particularly concerning is the increasing and spreading resistance to widely used antifungal agents such

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as fluconazole and echinocandins [12] [13]. The declining efficacy of fluconazole, especially among AIDS patients [14], highlights the urgent need for novel antifungal agents. To address these limitations, recent research has focused on developing compounds and therapeutic strategies, including agents that can target both fungal cells and their biofilms, to meet these challenges [15]. Benzimidazole derivatives have demonstrated a wide range of pharmacological properties, including antifungal, antibacterial, antiviral and anticancer activities [16] [17] [18] [19] [20]. Similarly, imidazopyridines have shown important therapeutic potential, such as calcium antagonists [21], anticancer agents [22] [23], antifungals [24], anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity [25]. Additionally, phenylhydrazone-based molecules are known for their anti-infective and antifungal properties, and are present in drugs such as zinoconazole and other experimental compounds [26] [27]. The present study focuses on the design, synthesis and antifungal evaluation of benzimidazole and its isostere imidazopyridine-based *N*-acylhydrazones derivatives. These hybrid molecules were developed by combining the pharmacologically active cores of benzimidazole or imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine with the phenylhydrazone moiety, aiming to enhance their antifungal efficacy [28] [29]. By structurally integrating these bioactive fragments, this work seeks to develop new antifungal agents capable of overcoming the limitations of existing therapies. The study contributes to ongoing efforts to discover safer and more effective treatments for fungal infections, particularly those complicated by resistance and biofilm formation.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

2.1.1. Chemistry Material

All chemicals were purchased from Aldrich Chemical, Fischer Scientific (France), and were used without further purification unless otherwise stated. The reactions were followed by TLC on pre-coated Merck 60 F254 silica gel plates and revealed using a UV lamp (6 W, 254 nm, and/or 365 nm). The purification of the products was carried out on a Merck G60 silica gel column. Melting points (m.p., °C) were determined using a temperature gradient (40-265°C) Kofler bench. For all compounds, the Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectra of proton ¹H and carbon ¹³C were recorded on a Bruker 300 or 400 advance device. Tetramethylsilane (TMS) was used as a reference for chemical displacements expressed in δ (ppm). The NMR spectra description uses the following symbols: s (singlet), d (doublet), dd (double doublet), t (triplet), q (quadruplet), m (multiplet). The mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL JMS DX300 spectrometer in ESI mode (electrospray/quadrupolar ionization or ESI mass).

2.1.2. Biological materials

The antifungal activity of the synthesized compounds was evaluated using a clinical strain of *Candida albicans*, obtained from Angré University Hospital Center in Côte d'Ivoire. To assess the sensitivity of this strain, an antifungal susceptibility profile was established using the agar diffusion method [30], as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Antifungal susceptibility profile

A series of ten (10) benzimidazole or imidazopyridine-*N*-acylhydrazones derivatives were synthesized and evaluated for their antifungal activity.

2.2. Method

2.2.1. Chemical Method

Compounds **2** (sel d'isothiuronium-1*H*-benzimidazole), **3** (2-((benzylthio)methyl)-1*H*-benzimidazole), **4** (ethyl 2-(2-((benzylthio)methyl)-1*H*-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)acetate), **5** (2-(2-((benzylthio)methyl)-1*H*-benzimidazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide), **8** (2-(3-nitroimidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-2-yl)isothiuronium) **9** (ethyl 2-((3-nitroimidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-2-yl)thio)acetate) and **10** (3-nitroimidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-2-yl)thio)acetohydrazide) have already been reported [31,32].

General procedure for the synthesis of *N*-acylhydrazones benzimidazoles (6a-f) or *N*-acylhydrazones imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine 11a-b

In a 10 mL flask equipped with a magnetic stirrer, 2-(2-((benzylthio)methyl)-1*H*-benzimidazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide **5** (1eq, 1.123 mol) or 3-nitroimidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-2-yl)thio)acetohydrazide **10** (1eq, 1.23 mol) was dissolved in methanol. Benzaldehyde derivatives were added and two drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl). The reaction mixture was refluxed for one hour. After cooling to room temperature, the precipitate formed was filtered, dried and purified by silica column chromatography to give compounds **6** and **11**.

(*E*)-2-(2-((benzylthio)methyl)-1*H*-benzimidazol-1-yl)-*N*-((3-hydroxynaphthalen-2-yl)methylene)acetohydrazide (**11e**)

Yellow powder, yield= 80% m.p = 170-175°C, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 11.74 (ap+sp) (s, 1H, NH), 9.27 ap, 8.96 sp (s, 1H, CH=N), 8.85 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H, H_{Ar}), 8.36 (ap+sp) (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H, H_{Ar}), 7.97 – 7.14 (m, 13H, H_{Ar}), 5.61sp, 5.21ap (s, 2H, N-CH₂), 4.03 ap (s, 25H), 3.98 sp (s, 2H, CH₂), 3.76 ap, 3.73 sp (s, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 167.85 sp, 163.47 ap (C=O), 158.40, 157.41, 146.98, 143.81 ap, 142.43 sp (N=CH), 138.45, 133.42, 133.06, 131.97, 131.80, 129.56, 129.48, 128.82, 128.34, 127.37, 124.03, 122.90, 122.70, 122.29, 122.05, 121.74, 119.22, 110.78, 109.04, 45.54ap, 45.16sp (CH₂-N), 35.17, 27.14. HRMS(ESI): Calc for C₂₈H₂₄N₄NaO₂S (M+Na)⁺: 503.1222; Found: 503.1226.

(*E*)-2-(2-((benzylthio)methyl)-1*H*-benzimidazol-1-yl)-*N*-(2-hydroxybenzylidene) acetohydrazide (**6b**)

Beige powder, yield= 94% m.p = 186-188°C, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm): 11.70 ap, 10.94 sp (s, 1H, NH), 10.09 (ap+sp) (s, 1H, OH), 8.48 ap, 8.38 sp (s, 1H, N=CH), 7.88 – 6.86 (ap+sp) (m, 13H, H_{Ar}), 5.51 sp, 5.15 ap (s, 2H, N-CH₂), 3.98 ap, 3.95 sp (s, 2H, CH₂), 3.74 ap, 3.72 sp (s, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm): 168.22 (C=O), 157.89, 156.89, 151.91, 148.00, 142.36 (N=CH), 141.97, 138.49, 132.04, 131.77, 129.55, 129.48, 128.83, 127.37, 122.66, 122.00, 120.61, 119.87, 119.10, 116.65, 110.85, 45.45, 35.19, 27.12. HRMS(ESI): Calc for C₂₄H₂₂N₄NaO₂S (M+Na)⁺: 453.1821; Found: 453.1822

(*E*)-2-(2-((benzylthio)methyl)-1*H*-benzimidazol-1-yl)-*N*-(3-bromobenzylidene) acetohydrazide (**6c**)

Beige powder, yield= 82% m.p.= 218-220°C, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 11.89 (ap+sp) (s, 1H, NH); 8.24 ap, 8.06 sp (s, 1H, CH=N); 7.78 (ap+sp) (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 2H, H_{Ar}); 7.68–7.59 (ap+sp) (m, 1H, H_{Ar}); 7.54–7.15 (ap+sp) (m, 10H, H_{Ar}); 5.56 sp, 5.13 ap (s, 2H, N-CH₂); 3.98 (ap+sp) (s, 2H, CH₂); 3.74 ap, 3.71 sp (s, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm): 168.79 sp, 163.91 ap (C=O), 151.99, 142.84, 142.39 (N=CH), 138.49, 136.97, 136.86, 133.05, 131.43, 129.49, 128.82, 127.38, 126.87, 122.75, 122.66, 122.02, 119.17, 110.86, 45.08, 35.19, 27.13. HRMS(ESI): Calc for C₂₄H₂₁BrN₄NaOS (M+Na)⁺: 515.0628; Found: 515.0619

(*E*)-2-(2-((benzylthio)methyl)-1*H*-benzimidazol-1-yl)-*N*-(4-nitrobenzylidene)acetohydrazide (**6d**)

Yellow powder, yield= 90% m.p. = 224-226°C, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 8.38 ap, 8.19 sp (s, 1H, N=CH), 8.33 (ap+sp) (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H, H_{Ar}), 8.07 (ap+sp) (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H, H_{Ar}), 7.99 (ap+sp) (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 1H, H_{Ar}), 7.69 – 7.61 (ap+sp) (m, 1H, H_{Ar}), 7.56 – 7.47 (ap+sp) (m, 1H, H_{Ar}), 7.44 – 7.16 (ap+sp) (m, 6H, H_{Ar}), 5.59 sp, 5.16 ap (s, 2H, N-CH₂), 3.97 (ap+sp) (s, 2H, CH₂), 3.74 ap (s, 2H, CH₂), 3.71 sp (s, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm): 169.05 (C=O), 152.00, 148.33, 145.56, 142.38 (N=CH), 142.17, 140.80, 138.48, 136.85, 129.49, 128.83, 128.47, 127.39, 124.51, 122.75, 122.05, 119.21, 110.81, 45.06, 35.17, 27.10. HRMS (ESI): Calc for C₂₄H₂₁N₅NaO₃S (M+Na)⁺: 482.1123; Found: 482.1128

(E)-N-(4-(benzylthio)benzylidene)-2-(2-((benzylthio)methyl)-1H-benzimidazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (6e)

Khaki powder, yield= 82% m.p. = 178-180°C, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 11.87 ap, 11.77 sp (s, 1H, NH), 8.24 ap, 8.05 sp (s, 1H, CH=N), 7.68 (ap+sp) (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 3H, H_{Ar}), 7.59 – 7.13 (ap+sp) (m, 15H, H_{Ar}), 5.54 sp, 5.13 ap (s, 2H, N-CH₂), 4.33 (ap+sp) (s, 2H, CH₂), 3.98 (ap+sp) (s, 2H, CH₂), 3.76 ap, 3.73 sp (s, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 168.49 sp (C=O); 152.00; 144.04 ap; 142.42 sp (CH=N); 139.43; 138.48; 137.65; 136.87; 131.80; 129.50; 129.31; 128.92; 128.84; 128.15; 128.03; 127.93; 127.65; 127.39; 122.70; 122.04; 119.20; 110.81; 45.00; 36.48; 35.24; 27.15. HRMS (ESI) : Calc for C₃₁H₂₈N₄NaOS₂ (M+Na)⁺ : 559.1943 ; Found : 559.1946

(E)-2-(2-((benzylthio)methyl)-1H-benzimidazol-1-yl)-N-((2-hydroxynaphthalen-2-yl)methylene)acetohydrazide (6f)

Yellow powder, yield= 80% m.p. = 170-175°C, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 11.74 (ap+sp) (s, 1H, NH), 9.27 ap, 8.96 sp (s, 1H, CH=N), 8.85 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H, H_{Ar}), 8.36 (ap+sp) (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H, H_{Ar}), 7.97 – 7.14 (m, 13H, H_{Ar}), 5.61 sp, 5.21 ap (s, 2H, N-CH₂), 4.03 ap (s, 25H), 3.98 sp (s, 2H, CH₂), 3.76 ap, 3.73 sp (s, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 167.85 sp, 163.47 ap (C=O), 158.40, 157.41, 146.98, 143.81ap, 142.43 sp (N=CH), 138.45, 133.42, 133.06, 131.97, 131.80, 129.56, 129.48, 128.82, 128.34, 127.37, 124.03, 122.90, 122.70, 122.29, 122.05, 121.74, 119.22, 110.78, 109.04, 45.54 ap, 45.16 sp (CH₂-N), 35.17, 27.14. HRMS(ESI): Calc for C₂₈H₂₄N₄NaO₂S (M+Na)⁺: 503.1222; Found: 503.1226

(E)-2-(3-Nitro-*H*-imidazo[1.2-*a*]pyridin-2-ylthio)-*N*-benzylideneacetohydrazide (11a)

Orange powder. m.p = 232-234°C; yield = 79%, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) 11.77 ap, 11.67 sp (s, 1H; NH), 9.34 (sp + ap) (dt, *J* = 6.9, 1.1 Hz, 1H; H_{Ar}), 8.22 ap, 8.05 sp (s, 1H; N=CH), 7.90 – 7.77 (sp + ap) (m, 2H; H_{Ar}), 7.71 (sp + ap) (td, *J* = 3.8; 2.2 Hz, 2H; H_{Ar}), 7.51–7.34 (sp + ap) (m, 4H; H_{Ar}), 4.63 sp, 4.22 ap (s, 2H, S-CH₂). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) 169.39 sp, 164.18 ap (C=O), 153.54 sp, 153.15 ap (N=CH), 147.44, 146.23, 144.16, 134.53, 134.48, 133.52sp, 133.46 ap (C_{Ar}), 130.60 sp, 130.44 ap (C_{Ar}), 129.29, 128.65 sp, 128.40 ap (C_{Ar}), 127.58, 127.34, 11697 sp, 116.87 ap (C_{Ar}), 116.79, 33.95 ap, 33.08 sp (SCH₂). HRMS (ESI):Calc for [M + Na⁺] C₁₆H₁₃N₅NaO₃S = 378.0521. Found = 378.0525.

(E)-N-(2-Hydroxybenzylidene)2-(3-nitro-*H*-imidazo[1.2-*a*]pyridin-2-ylthio) acetohydrazide (11b)

Brown powder, m.p. = 238-240°C, yield = 69%, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) 11.64 sp (s, 1H; OH), 11.14 ap, 11.01 sp (s, 1H; NH), 10.13 ap (s, 1H, OH), 9.35 (sp-ap) (m, 1H; H_{Ar}), 8.44 ap, 8.36 sp (s, 1H; N=CH), 7.90–7.77 (sp-ap) (m, 4H; H_{Ar}), 7.70 (sp-ap) (ddd, *J* = 8.1, 4.8, 1.6 Hz, 1H, H_{Ar}), 7.54 (dd, *J* = 8.0, 1.7 Hz, 1H; H_{Ar}), 7.49–7.35 (m, 2H; H_{Ar}),

7.35–7.20 (m, 2H, H_{Ar}), 7.03–6.80 (m, 5H, H_{Ar}), 4.61 sp, 4.23 ap(s, 2H, S-CH₂).¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) 169.03 sp, 164.07 ap (C=O), 163.28 ap, 159.10 sp (C-OH), 157.73, 156.89, 153.54 sp, 153.06 ap (N=CH), 147.65, 146.24, 141.78, 133.72, 133.53, 133.47, 131.94, 131.72, 131.32, 129.68, 128.54, 126.86, 120.51, 120.09, 119.91, 119.84, 119.08, 118.64, 116.99, 116.80, 116.64, 33.67ap, 33.12sp (SCH₂), HRMS (ESI): Calc for [M + H⁺] C₁₆H₁₄N₅O₄S = 372.0843. Found = 372.0839.

(E)-2-(3-Nitro-*H*-imidazo[1.2-*a*]pyridin-2-ylthio)-*N*-(4-[benzylthio] benzylidene)acetohydrazide (11c)

Khaki powder; m.p. = 250-252°C; yield = 72%. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) 11.77 ap, 11.62 sp (s, 1H, NH), 9.35 (sp + ap) (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H, H_{Ar}). 8.17 ap, 8.00 sp (s, 1H, N=CH-), 7.91–7.80 (sp + ap) (m, 2H, H_{Ar}), 7.66–7.56 (sp + ap) (m, 2H, H_{Ar}), 7.46–7.39(sp + ap) (m, 5H, H_{Ar}), 7.34–7.27 (sp + ap) (m, 2H, H_{Ar}), 7.27–7.23 (sp + ap) (m, 1H, H_{Ar}), 4.62 sp, 4.31 ap (s, 2H, S-CH₂), 4.39 sp, 4.21 ap (s, 2H, S-CH₂). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) 168.80 sp, 163.57 ap (C=O), 153.07 sp, 152.69 ap (N=CH-), 146.35 sp, 145.76 ap (C_{Ar}), 143.10, 139.10 sp, 138.82 ap (C_{Ar}), 137.15 sp, 137.09 ap (C_{Ar}), 133.00, 131.32, 129.85, 128.86 sp, 128.83 ap (C_{Ar}), 128.53 sp, 128.44 ap (C_{Ar}), 128.22, 127.96, 127.66, 127.54 sp, 127.51 ap (C_{Ar}), 127.27 sp, 127.16 ap (C_{Ar}), 126.43, 116.50 sp, 116.33 ap (C_{Ar}), 35.92, 33.49 ap, 32.58 sp (S-CH₂). HRMS (ESI): Calc for [M + Na⁺] C₂₃H₁₉N₅NaO₃S₂ = 500.1021. Found = 500.1025.

(E)-2-(3-Nitro-*H*-imidazo[1.2-*a*]pyridin-2-ylthio)-*N*'-(4-[4-methylbenzyloxy] benzylidene) acetohydrazide (11d)

Khaki powder; m.p. = 216-218°C; yield = 72%; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) 11.65 ap, 11.55 sp (s, 1H, NH), 9.33 (sp + ap) (dt, *J* = 6.9, 1.1 Hz, 1H, H_{Ar}), 8.15 ap, 7.98 sp (s, 1H, N=CH-), 7.88–7.75 (sp + ap) (m, 2H, H_{Ar}), 7.62 (sp + ap) (dd, *J* = 8.8, 2.2 Hz, 2H, H_{Ar}), 7.40 (sp + ap) (ddd, *J* = 6.6, 5.4, 2.9 Hz, 1H, H_{Ar}), 7.33 (sp + ap) (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H, H_{Ar}),

7.18 (sp + ap) (d, J = 7.8 Hz, 2H, HAr), 7.05 (sp + ap) (dd, J = 8.9, 2.2 Hz, 2H, HAr), 5.08 (sp +- ap) (s, 2H, O-CH₂), 4.60 sp, 4.19 ap (s, 2H, S-CH₂), 2.29 sp, 2.08 ap (s, 3H, CH₃), ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm) 168.65 sp, 163.39 ap (C=O), 159.99 sp, 159.82 ap (CAr), 153.15 sp, 152.74 ap (N=CH-), 146.80, 145.77, 143.48, 137.20, 133.69, 133.05 sp, 132.99 ap (CAr), 129.01, 128.71, 128.44, 128.20, 127.94 sp, 127.87 ap, 126.76, 116.49, 116.39 sp, 116.33 ap (CAr), 115.18, 69.27, 33.52 ap, 32.63 sp (S-CH₂), 20.79. HRMS (ESI): Calc for [M + H⁺] C₂₄H₂₂N₅O₄S = 476.0956. Found = 476.0952.

2.2.2. Biological Methods

The compounds were solubilized using either dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) or distilled water, and tested against a clinical strain of *Candida albicans*. Fluconazole was used as the reference antifungal agent. The fungal strain was supplied and identified by the Parasitology-Mycology Unit of the Medical Biology Department at Angré University Hospital. Antifungal activity of our compounds was determined using the broth microdilution method in 96-well microplates, following a standard procedure to establish the Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MICs) of the compounds. This method involves exposing *Candida albicans* inoculum to a series of compound dilutions and monitoring fungal growth inhibition through a colorimetric assay of germ dehydrogenase activity using Methyl Thiazolyl Tetrazolium (MTT) chloride. This coloration (violet) comes from the mitochondrial activity of active living cells. From 7-day-old colonies of *Candida albicans* grown on Sabouraud chloramphenicol agar, a stock Conidia suspension was vortexed vigorously for 15-20 seconds in 5 mL of Tryptone Soy Broth (OXOID®). The conidial concentration was determined using a Malassez counting chamber, and adjusted to give a turbidity of 0.5 McFarland (0.4-5 × 10⁶ spores/mL). A 50-fold dilution of this suspension was prepared to obtain a working concentration of approx. 0.08-1 × 10⁵ CFU/mL [33]. Stock solutions of the test compounds were prepared in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) or water at 1 mg/mL. In the first row of each microplate, 100 μL of the stock solution was added. All remaining wells received 50 μL of Tryptone Soy Broth. Serial dilutions were performed by transferring 50 μL from one well to the next across the row. Each well then received 50 μL of the diluted fungal inoculum. The 96-well plates were incubated at 37°C for 7 days. After incubation, 40 μL of an aqueous solution of MTT aqueous solution at a concentration of 2.5 mg/mL was added to each well, followed by an additional 24-hours incubation at 37°C. The MTT solution, which is initially yellow turns purple in wells where fungal cells remain viable, due to mitochondrial dehydrogenase activity (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Dilution on microplates in liquid medium

The MIC was defined as the lowest concentration of the compound that prevented this color change, indicating complete growth inhibition [34] [35] [36]. All samples were duplicated and the tests were repeated and improved twice.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Chemistry

We successfully synthesized two series of *N*-acylhydrazones derivatives: benzimidazole-based (6a-f) and imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine-based *N*-acylhydrazones (11a-d) (as outlined in Figure 3 and Figure 4). The synthetic route to the benzimidazole derivatives began with the preparation of the isothiuronium salt (2), following the procedure reported by Farid et al [31]. Specifically, 2-chloromethyl 1*H*-benzimidazole (1) was reacted with thiourea under reflux in acetonitrile for 1.5 hours, yielding salt (2) in 89% yield. Next intermediate (3) was obtained according to a method described by Oleynik et al. [32]. Salt (2) underwent alkylation with benzyl chloride in a water-ethanol mixture in the presence of sodium hydroxide (NaOH). Ester intermediate (4) was then synthesized by a nucleophilic substitution between compound (3) and ethyl 2-chloroacetate using potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃) in dimethylformamide (DMF).

This step provided ester (4) in 92% yield. Hydrazone (5) was subsequently prepared by refluxing ester (4) with hydrazine monohydrate in ethanol for 5 hours, affording the product in 90% yield. Condensation of hydrazone (5) with a series of substituted aromatic aldehydes under reflux in methanol for 1 hour gave the desired *N*-acylhydrazone derivatives (6a-f), with yields ranging from 50 to 94% (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Synthesis route of benzimidazole-*N*-acylhydrazones derivatives

Reaction conditions: (i) Thiourea, MeCN, reflux, 2h; (ii) Benzyl chloride, NaOH, EtOH/H₂O, reflux 2h; (iii) ClCH₂CO₂Et, K₂CO₃, DMF, 2h; (iv) NH₂-NH₂, EtOH, reflux 5h; (v) Ar-COH, MeOH, reflux 1h

The imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-based *N*-acylhydrazone derivatives (11a-d) were synthesized through a four-step pathway starting from a 3-nitro-substituted imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine scaffold (Figure 4). The introduction of a nitro group (-NO₂) at position 3 served to electronically deactivate position 2, thereby promoting aromatic nucleophilic substitution reaction. In the first step, 2-chloro-3-nitroimidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine (7) was reacted with thiourea under conditions analogous to those used for the benzimidazole series. This reaction afforded the isothioureonium salt of 3-nitroimidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine (8) in 96% yield [31]. Subsequently, salt (8) was treated with ethyl 2-chloroacetate under basic conditions in a refluxing water-ethanol mixture, leading to the formation of thioester (9) in 73% yield. Conversion of the ester (9) to the corresponding hydrazone (10) was achieved through reaction with hydrazine hydrate, yielding in 52% yield.

Finally, the condensation of hydrazone (10) with a series of substituted aromatic aldehydes in methanol under reflux for 1 hour gave the target *N*-acylhydrazone derivatives (11a-d). The reactions proceeded smoothly, affording products in moderate to good yields ranging from 52% to 82% (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Synthesis route of *N*-acylhydrazone imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine derivatives

Reaction conditions: (i) Thiourea, MeCN, reflux; 48 h; (ii) ClCH₂CO₂Et, NaOH, EtOH/H₂O, reflux 1h; (iii) NH₂-NH₂, EtOH, reflux 5h; (iv) Ar-COH, MeOH, reflux 1h.

The structures of key intermediates and final benzimidazole-based derivatives (compounds 3, 4, 5 and 6a-f) were confirmed using spectroscopic analyses such as ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and High-Resolution Mass spectrometry (HRMS). In the ^1H NMR spectrum of compound (3), two singlets were observed at 3.71 and 3.93 ppm, corresponding to the two methylene protons (CH_2). These assignments were supported by ^{13}C NMR spectrum. The spectrum which showed two distinct signals at 27 and 35 ppm, confirming the presence of two methylene (CH_2) carbons. For compound (4), the ^1H NMR spectrum showed characteristic signals of an ethoxy group: a quadruplet at 4.20 ppm ($-\text{CH}_2-$) and a triplet at 1.26 ppm ($-\text{CH}_3$), confirming successful ester formation. In compound (5), analysis of the ^1H NMR spectrum shows the disappearance of ethoxy signals and the appearance of new peaks supported the conversion to the hydrazide. Specifically, two signals, one at 9.54 ppm attributable to the hydrazide NH proton, and another at 4.39 ppm assigned to NH_2 protons, confirming successful hydrazinolysis of the ester.

The imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine-based (11a-d) were also characterized by ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and HRMS. In the ^1H NMR spectrum of intermediate (9) a singlet at 4.12 ppm was observed, corresponding to the two methylene protons located between the sulfur atom and the ester function ($\text{S}-\text{CH}_2-\text{COOEt}$). The ethoxy group protons of the ester function appeared as a quadruplet at 4.24 ppm ($-\text{CH}_2-$) and a triplet at 1.30 ppm ($-\text{CH}_3$), confirming the presence of the ester functionality. These changes clearly indicated successful conversion of the ester into the hydrazide. For hydrazide (10), the ^1H NMR spectrum revealed the disappearance of the ethoxy signals and the appearance of two broad singlets at 4.32 and 7.42 ppm, corresponding to the amine ($-\text{NH}_2$) and hydrazide ($-\text{NH}-\text{C}=\text{O}$) protons, respectively.

In the final *N*-acylhydrazone derivatives (6a-f and 11a-d), ^1H NMR spectra exhibited a notable duplication of signals associated with three adjacent groups in the acylhydrazone moiety: the amide NH, the azomethine ($\text{N}=\text{CH}$), and the methylene group ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}-$) [37]. This duplication is consistent with the presence of two conformers: *syn*-periplanar (*sp* E) and *anti*-periplanar E (*ap* E) in an approximate 66:34 % ratio, respectively. Interestingly, in compounds featuring an ortho-hydroxy substituent on the aromatic acyl group, the *ap* E conformer became slightly predominant. This shift is likely due to additional stabilization through intramolecular hydrogen bonding, involving the ortho-hydroxyl proton and both the azomethine nitrogen and the adjacent carbonyl oxygen lone pairs. Such conformational behavior reflects the dynamic structural versatility of the *N*-acylhydrazone motif, which may influence biological activity.

3.2. Anticandidal activities

The anticandidal activity of the synthesized compounds was compared with the reference drug Fluconazole. Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MICs) were initially determined in $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (mass/volume) but were subsequently converted to micromolar (μM) to enable a more accurate comparison of biological activity. This conversion is essential because MIC values expressed in mass per volume ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) do not account for molecular weight differences among compounds. Expressing MICs in μM allows for normalization based on molecular concentration, thus providing a more precise evaluation of antifungal efficacy on a per-molecule basis. The results of the anticandidal activity obtained after evaluation of benzimidazole *N*-acylhydrazones (6a-f) and imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine *N*-acylhydrazones (11a-d) against the clinical strain of *Candida Albicans* are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Anticandidal activity of *N*-acylhydrazones derivatives (6a-f and 11a-d)

Compounds	General structure	Ar	Molecular weight (g/mol)	MIC ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	MIC (μM)
6a		Naphtalen-2-ol	480.586	12.5	26.009
6b		4-Hydroxyphenyl	430.526	25	58.068
6c		2-Hydroxyphenyl	430.526	25	58.068
6d		4-Nitrophenyl	459.524	25	54.404
6e		3-Bromophenyl	493.423	25	50.666
6f		(4-methylbenzyl)(phenyl)sulfane	550.739	25	45.393

11a		Phenyl	355.372	25	70.034
11b		2-Hydroxyphenyl	371.371	25	67.318
11c		(4-methylbenzyl)(phenyl)sulfane	491.584	25	50.856
11d		1-methyl-4-(phenoxyethyl)benzene	461.496	25	54.171
Fluconazole			306.276	25	81.62

The antifungal evaluation demonstrated that both benzimidazole *N*-acylhydrazone (**6a-f**) and imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine *N*-acylhydrazone (**11a-d**) derivatives exhibit significant activity against the clinical strain of *Candida albicans*, with MICs ranging from 26.009 μM to 70.034 μM . To gain further insight into the molecular features influencing antifungal efficacy, a structure-activity relationship (SAR) analysis was undertaken. The aim is to establish correlations between specific structural elements and observed biological activity, in order to identify functional groups or scaffolds that contribute to the induction or enhance antifungal potential. For this discussion, MIC values expressed in micromolar units are used as a direct indicator of antifungal potency: the lower the MIC, the more active the compound. Our findings indicate that both the heterocyclic core (benzimidazole vs. imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine) and the nature of the aromatic ring attached *via* the hydrazone linkage significantly influence biological activity against *C. Albicans* strains. Within the benzimidazole *N*-acylhydrazone series (**6a-f**), variation in antifungal efficacy was clearly observed, suggesting that substituents on the aryl moiety play a pivotal role. Analysis of this series reveals that:

Compound **6a**, bearing a naphthalen-2-yl moiety at the hydrazone position showed the highest antifungal activity in the series with an MIC of 26.009 μM . This strong performance is likely due to the extended π -system and high lipophilicity of the naphthyl ring, which may promote favorable van der Waals or hydrophobic interactions with the lipid-rich fungal membrane.

Substitution of the naphthyl group with its monocyclic analogs, 2-hydroxyphenyl (compound **6b**) and 4-hydroxyphenyl (compound **6c**), led to a marked decrease in activity, both exhibiting identical MICs of 58.068 μM . These results suggest that the reduction in molecular volume and increased hydrophilicity of the phenolic moieties diminish antifungal efficacy. The hydroxylated derivatives proved 2 times less effective than compound **6a**. The presence of hydroxyl groups, capable of hydrogen bonding, appears unfavorable in this scaffold.

Replacing the hydroxyl group in **6c** with a nitro group in compound **6d** (4-nitrophenyl) slightly improved activity (MIC = 54.404 μM). This modest gain may be attributed to the intrinsic antimicrobial properties of nitro groups, as evidenced in related nitroimidazole-based drugs.

Further modification by introducing a halogenated phenyl in compound **6e** (3-bromophenyl) did not significantly alter antifungal potency, with an MIC also at 54.404 μM . This suggests that, unlike in some azole antifungals, halogenation at this position does not enhance efficacy in this series.

Interestingly, compound **6f**, which incorporates a 4-methylbenzyl(phenyl)sulfane moiety, displayed the second-best activity (MIC = 45.393 μM). This result likely reflects the increased lipophilicity imparted by the methyl and sulfane functionalities, which may enhance membrane permeability and compound diffusion through the fungal cell wall.

Replacing the benzimidazole core with the isosteric imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine scaffold, and repositioning the acetothiohydrazone functionality to position 2, resulted in derivatives (11a-d) that retained antifungal activity, albeit with generally higher MIC values (50.856-70.034 μM), suggesting slightly reduced potency compared to their benzimidazole counterparts. In addition, the structure-activity relationships undertaken enabled us to establish:

Compound 11a, bearing an unsubstituted phenyl ring, displayed the lowest activity in the series (MIC = 70.034 μM). The limited efficacy may be due to the absence of lipophilic or electron-donating substituents that enhance cell permeability. A minor improvement was observed in compound 11b, where substitution with a 2-hydroxyphenyl group lowered the MIC to 67.318 μM . However, as in the benzimidazole series, the presence of hydrophilic hydroxyl groups did not significantly enhance activity.

Introduction of a 4-methylbenzyl(phenyl)sulfane moiety in compound 11c resulted in a notable increase in antifungal activity (MIC = 50.856 μM), mirroring the trend observed in compound 6f. The result reinforces the beneficial role of the sulfane group in enhancing lipophilic interactions with fungal membranes.

Compound 11d, bearing a closely related 1-methyl-4-(phenyl)sulfanylbenzene group, also showed good activity (MIC = 54.171 μM), confirming the pharmacological relevance of aryl sulfur-containing substituents in promoting antifungal efficacy.

4. Conclusion

This study reports the successful design and antifungal evaluation of two novel series of *N*-acylhydrazone derivatives based on benzimidazole and imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine scaffolds. Spectroscopic analyses confirmed the structures and conformational behavior of the synthesized compounds, which were obtained as mixtures of *E*-conformers. Biological assessment against *Candida albicans* revealed variable antifungal activities, strongly influenced by both the nature of the heterocycle and the substituents on the acylhydrazone moiety. Among the benzimidazole derivatives, compound 6a, featuring a naphthalen-2-ol group, demonstrated the most potent activity, underscoring the importance of bulky, lipophilic aromatic systems in facilitating interaction with fungal membranes. Similarly, derivatives incorporating sulfur-based aryl substituents (6f, 11c, and 11d) displayed enhanced antifungal efficacy, supporting their relevance in pharmacomodulation strategies.

These findings provide valuable insights into the structure–activity relationships of *N*-acylhydrazone compounds and pave the way for the development of optimized antifungal agents with improved potency and selectivity. Future work will focus on broadening the antifungal spectrum, assessing cytotoxicity, and exploring molecular mechanisms of action.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Author contributions

T.E.C., P.A.A and E.A performed the synthesis, purification of all the compounds and contributed to the writing of the manuscript. S.C. conceptualized the biological study, SC participated in the design and conceptualization of the work, and revised the manuscript, while C.S supervised the overall project.

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